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ADVANTAGES OF THE VIRTUAL LABORATORY IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS.

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Ferghana branch of TUIT named after Muhammad al-Khorazmi

Annotation. This article deals with the problem of informatization of the field of education and the lack of pedagogical and methodological material for the use of virtual reality in the educational process. Virtual reality is one of the high-tech directions of the digital economy, and the demand in modern society is increasing. At the same time, it can be seen that there is a lack of qualified personnel with the ability to use virtual reality in the field of education. This article shows that some problems of educational information can be solved with the help of virtual reality.

Keywords: informatization of education, educational technologies, information and communication technologies, information models, elective courses, project method, virtual reality.

VIRTUAL LABORATORIYANING TA'LIM JARAYONIDAGI AFZALLIKLARI.

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada ta'lim sohasini axborotlashtirish muammosi va o'quv jarayonida virtual reallikdan foydalanish uchun pedagogik va uslubiy materialning yetishmasligi bilan bog'liq. Virtual reallik raqamli iqtisodiyotning yuqori texnologiyali yo'nalishlaridan biri bo'lib, zamonaviy jamiyatda talab ortib bormoqda. Shu bilan birga, ta'lim sohasida virtual reallikdan foydalanish qobiliyatiga ega malakali kadrlar yetishmasligini ko'rish mumkin. Ushbu maqolada ta'limni axborotlashtirishning ba'zi muammolarini virtual haqiqat yordamida hal qilish mumkinligi ko'rsatilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: ta'limni axborotlashtirish, ta'lim texnologiyalari, axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari, axborot modellari, tanlov kurslari, loyiha usuli, virtual reallik.

Currently, various information and communication technologies are radically changing the way we interact with large amounts of data. They provide sample opportunities to create artificial environments in which a person is immersed, and which affect his knowledge, skills and abilities. This fact is reflected in the emergence of new learning technologies. Immersive technologies in education make it possible to create a direct connection between the perception of the student and the content, creating conditions for a sense of presence and participation in the proposed events. The essence of these technologies is revealed through the concepts of virtual, augmented and mixed reality.

The article provides an overview of modern information and communication technologies in education, including the use of virtual, augmented and mixed reality. The problems of informatization of education are revealed. It is shown that with the help of virtual, augmented and mixed reality, some of these problems can be solved. Informatization of many spheres of life, including education, is a characteristic feature of the 21st century. The rapid development of technology could not but affect the educational process.

New directions in the development of informatization in education include artificial intelligence, which makes it possible to identify patterns and trends in learning and student behavior, provide analysis and communication of learning outcomes, chatbots, blockchain technology, mobile devices, collaborative virtual reality, the use of other technologically advanced solutions and their integration into the infrastructure university, as well as the effective use of existing resources of the educational institution. It is assumed that the result of the informatization of education is the creation of an information society in which intelligence and knowledge will play the main role. A means of mastering the existing and new areas of informatization of education, extracting the maximum benefits of their use are various information and communication technologies (ICT), constantly created and improved.

Didactic features of the use of ICT have a number of advantages:

- 1) independent planning of training time;
- 2) the possibility of using modern learning technologies;
- 3) providing information in blocks, based on the individual characteristics of students;
- 4) increasing the financial, spatial, linguistic and temporal accessibility of education;
- 5) automation of the procedure for monitoring knowledge, skills and abilities with an increase in its objectivity and efficiency;

6) demonstration of the achievements of science and technology in a virtual format.

The process of informatization of education, the development and use of ICT should be directed so that new educational models contribute to the creative development of students and ensure rapid decision-making. The choice and support of such areas is one of the most difficult tasks of informatization of modern society. In particular, a large unstructured amount of information necessitates the formation of selectivity in relation to the incoming information and the expediency of its application. A number of negative consequences of the use of ICT in the educational process can be divided into three areas [1].

1. Medical.

Information technology affects the health of the student both in school and outside of school. Proceeding from this, the education of the information culture of students, which includes the organization and control of the safe use of ICT, becomes significant.

2. Social.

Individualization of learning is accompanied by a reduction in social ties due to the transition to possible non-verbal communication when working with an electronic educational resource.

3. Pedagogical.

ICT tools in education outside the educational institution are characterized by reduced motivation due to the conditions of the natural environment, a possible loss of control on the part of the pedagogical institution of the psychological state of the student. There is an increase in the possibility of using devices outside of educational purposes, loss of attention, the level of cognitive distortion, as well as rapid fatigue from educational activities.

To overcome possible negative consequences in the learning process using information and communication technologies, it is necessary to apply and develop complexes of organizational, psychological-pedagogical and medical-social measures for the well-being of students. The search and development of forms of such events, methods of their implementation, including with the help of information technology, is also one of the global pedagogical problems of the process of informatization of education.

Modeling allows you to study objects in different fields, so most of the tasks proposed by the authors of teaching aids are considered on the basis of the fields of physics, economics, biology, chemistry, medicine, aviation, astronautics, etc. Conducting a computer experiment in these disciplines prepares and develops interest in technical innovation. The described research activity in conjunction with interdisciplinary connections contributes to the self-determination of students in the professional field, including the most popular scientific and technical ones.

When studying modeling, various types of information models are considered:

- 1) verbal;
- 2) graphic;
- 3) tabular;
- 4) algorithmic;
- 5) imitation, etc.

One of the recommended forms of organizing training in computer modeling is a combination of lecture, laboratory and test tasks, which can be organized using information technology. On the basis of theoretical material, problematic learning situations are created that require active independent activity from students. Performing practical tasks deepens the skill of independently compiling an algorithm and writing programs, as well as working with various software (SW), such as text and graphic editors.

The most effective pedagogical technology for conducting laboratory work is the project method. Such activity develops the ability to plan one's work to achieve the set goal, self-learning, develops creative abilities, communication skills, logical thinking and increases learning motivation.

The development of tabular forms of information presentation are databases and spreadsheets. Database design consists in building and using an information model of a certain structure, usually of a relational type, as well as maintenance by means of database management systems. Electronic tables are considered from the point of view of the implementation of the mathematical model of the system in order to conduct a numerical experiment.

The effectiveness of teaching information technology depends on many factors that arise in the process of joint work of students and teachers. The result is influenced by the flexible skills of the teacher. Among them, one can emphasize critical analysis and cooperation, motivation for additional efforts, individual approach and trusting relationships, the achievement of which can be a problem in the information field of education. It is necessary to have the ability to change teaching methods if the goals of the students have not been achieved. The leading task is to create a safe educational environment where complex but achievable learning goals are set. Educational institutions are equipped and actively use information technologies throughout the infrastructure: a multimedia room, voting systems, video studios, web conferences, robotics laboratories, 3D printers, mobile devices and others [2].

Consider the following innovative technologies used for information technology education:

1. With case technology, educational material is presented in the form of sets (cases), the process of solving which takes place in the form of independent or team work. The process is accompanied by a consultation of a teacher who carries out methodological and organizational work. This method is effective in terms of collecting information, analyzing the problem from different points of view through discussions, forming a hypothesis, conclusions and conclusions.

2. Game technologies are considered as a set of methods for using the game in the educational process. This is a productive way to enhance cognitive activity and motivate students. They allow for group and individual work, joint discussion, knowledge control and the creation of game situations. As a game task, the didactic goal of the lesson is set, which will need to be achieved at the end of the game.

3. Educational technology STEAM education is a synthesis of science, technology, engineering, creativity and mathematics. This is due to the acute shortage of specialists in high-tech industries, where comprehensive training is needed. The technology provides a blended learning environment and demonstrates the application of the scientific method to daily life through a wide range of hands-on activities. Virtual reality (VR) is an interactive environment with a complete immersion of the user in the virtual world through the influence, change and interaction with information received through the channels of perception, special headsets. An example of a headset that provides this type is the famous Oculus Rift, which gave an active and dramatic development of this technology.

MR technology (Mixed Reality) is the coexistence of VR and AR creating a hybrid of realities. The headset scans the world around, recognizes objects and builds their three-dimensional models, allowing you to interact with the real world through the virtual. Learning with the use of VR occurs through the presence of a student in a virtual environment. It allows you to implement various types of activities in the educational process. This technology is currently considered to be actively developing and innovative. Its application in education has certain difficulties:

- 1) auditorium equipment,
- 2) educational products.

The educational program requires a permanent addition, which can be implemented within the framework of the planned elective courses for students. With the help of elective courses, one can not only improve learning outcomes, but also partially alleviate the acuteness of the problems posed to modern society

by informatization. There are several types of elective courses. Subject courses are aimed at developing and deepening knowledge in a basic academic subject, and interdisciplinary courses immerse in tasks, the solution of which requires the application of knowledge and skills of several disciplines. Therefore, one of the most important tasks of an educational institution is to provide a sufficient number of elective courses that effectively form the educational competencies of students.

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